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T3.2 EASTERN SLOVENIA REGIONAL REPORT

Version: 1.0

Work package: 3

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**Funded by
the European Union**

JustWind4All is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them (Grant Agreement 101083936).

Dissemination Level	Public
Work Package	WP3 Case studies
Type	Milestone
Number of Pages	43
Author names and affiliations	Iva Dekic Tajnsek, Consensus (CONS) Andrej Drapal, Consensus (CONS)
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Description	A case study of the development of wind energy governance in Eastern Slovenia.

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DISCLAIMER AND FORWARD

This case study about wind energy developments in Eastern Slovenia has been produced for the Horizon Europe JustWind4All (JW4A) project as part of WP3 task 3.2. The task aims to develop an understanding of regional challenges and opportunities around wind energy governance over the past 5-10 years to formulate key recommendations to foster energy citizenship in effective and just wind energy governance regionally. It is based on a mixed method approach including for each region: document reviews (around 50), 5-10 interviews with wind energy governance actors and a media and policy analysis. A comparative analysis across cases and across the project's regions allows for a better understanding of challenges and opportunities around effective and just wind energy governance.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 COUNTRY CONTEXT

1.1.1 ENERGY SYSTEM

Slovenia has one of the lowest wind energy exploitation rates in Europe. There are only two operating wind turbines in Slovenia – a 2.3-megawatt and 0.9-megawatt installation, both in the West Slovenia region, near the Karst plateau Nanos. Slovenia covers approximately half of its domestic energy needs with domestic production (53 % in 2021), with its main import being petroleum products (SURS, 2022). At the moment of writing, Slovenia is mostly self-sufficient in its electricity production, however with the upcoming closure of coal fired plants in 2033 and the expected increase in electricity use due to the electrification of heating, cooling and transport, as well as digitalisation, new power plants need to be built to ensure sufficient electricity in future.

Slovenia relies heavily on three energy sources in its electricity production: hydro, nuclear and coal. Among those, nuclear energy is the leading source in energy production (over 40 %), however half of the energy produced in Slovenia's sole nuclear power plant is exported to Croatia, which is the co-owner of the plant (NEK, n. d.). Hydropower plants produce between 25 and 30 % of all electricity and the coal fired power plant produces approximately a third of all electricity in Slovenia (SURS, 2022).

Figure 1: Electricity production in Slovenia (2021)

Slovenia had implemented a National Renewable Action Plan aimed at achieving specific energy goals by 2020. The plan aimed to achieve a 25% share of energy generation from renewable sources in gross final energy consumption and aims to meet 39% of electricity demand through renewable energy sources (IEA, n. d.). In 2020, renewable energy sources were used to produce 33% of all electricity in Slovenia, missing the goal by 4 %. The majority of this was produced in hydropower plants, and only 2,2% through solar and wind (SURS,

2021). Additionally, in 2021, Slovenia achieved a renewable energy share of 19% and has failed to meet its 2020 target of 25% renewables share in final energy consumption, which includes electricity, transport and heating/cooling.

By 2030 Slovenia has set the target of 27% of renewables in total energy usage and 43% of renewables in final energy consumption.

1.1.1.1 Wind and Solar in Slovenia

Wind and solar energy account for approximately 2 % of the total energy produced in Slovenia. The plans for the upcoming decades focus on increasing the percentage of renewables. The focus lies mostly with solar energy. This preference has increased with the current coalition, elected in April of 2022. In July 2022, the infrastructure ministry was tasked by the government with drawing up a plan to increase photovoltaic capacity by 1,000 megawatts by 2025 in cooperation with national grid operator ELES and distribution system operator SODO, both nationally owned companies (Maček, 2022). Currently, most of Slovenia's solar capacities are small roof-mounted arrays, with larger solar projects having a strong opposition, similar to wind projects. While goals for the expansion of wind energy capacities were also set, there are little or no specific plans as to how to achieve the targets.

1.1.2 SUBSIDY SCHEMES

In Slovenia, the process of the deployment of RES follows a structured two-round tender process to determine support recipients and levels. Renewable production facilities, including hydro, connected to the grid after September 22, 2014, are eligible to participate in the annually published public call. Meanwhile, operators of renewable energy plants connected before this date have the option to sell their electricity to the Slovenian power market operator, Borzen, at a fixed "uniform annual price" known as the feed-in tariff or choose a premium tariff - operators of renewable energy plants with an installed capacity of up to 5 MW may choose to sell their electricity directly on the market instead of receiving the guaranteed purchase price (feed-in tariff). In this case, they will receive the so-called "operational support" (i.e. a premium tariff). Power plants with a capacity of more than 5 MW may only opt for this support scheme. The authority for tenders for the feed-in support scheme is The Slovenian Energy Agency (CMS Law, 2020).

Moreover, Slovenia organizes public calls for subsidy applications and offers loans to support projects in the renewable energy field. Renewable energy sources for heating purposes primarily receive support through loans and subsidies, while the promotion of renewable energy use in the transport sector relies on tax exemptions and loan opportunities (Reslegal, n. d.). The renewables subsidy program remains limited to small projects, however, developers may use other revenue streams such as different types of power purchase agreements (PPAs) (Climatescope, 2022).

The country prioritizes the integration of electricity from renewable energy sources into the grid, granting access to RES-E (Renewable Energy Sources for Electricity) installations with priority to the grid. In terms of grid usage, renewable energy is also given preference. However, it is essential to note that grid development lies within the jurisdiction of the grid operator and cannot be directly enforced.

Slovenia has implemented several policies aimed at fostering the development, installation, and utilization of renewable energy installations. These policies work in tandem to create

an environment conducive to the growth of renewable energy within the country (Reslegal, n. d.).

1.1.3 THE LEGAL DEVELOPMENT PROCESS OF WIND ENERGY PROJECTS IN SLOVENIA

The development and permitting process of a wind energy project depends heavily on its size. According to Article 50 of the Spatial Planning Act, power plants with a nominal electric power of at least 10 MW are considered to be spatial arrangements of national importance, and therefore should be part of the National Spatial Plan.

Municipalities are however responsible for smaller energy projects and their spatial arrangements.

In the diagram shown below, a process of acquiring permits for building and operating a wind farm is shown.

Figure 2: Process for acquiring permits for wind farm development in Slovenia

1.1.4 MAIN BARRIERS IN WIND ENERGY DEPLOYMENT

The first attempts to set up wind power plants in Slovenia date back more than ten years, but wind power plants were never favored by a large part of the public. In particular, the inhabitants of the places where these power plants are supposed to be located, the civil initiatives established for this purpose, and especially the Society for the Observation and Study of Birds of Slovenia (Dopps), loudly oppose any plans for the construction of wind power plants (Pavlin, 2017). The lack of strong and visible support for wind energy projects, lack of institutional support on regulations to support the development of wind energy increases the visibility of the opposition, while the support for specific wind farm developments come mostly from investors.

The second barrier, which has proven to deter the development of wind project, is the length and complexity of administrative processes. A 2022 report on barriers and best practices for

wind and solar electricity in the EU27 and UK, funded by the European Climate Foundation has ranked Slovenia just below EU average in terms of barriers blocking wind and solar energy projects. The biggest obstacle has shown to be the difficulty of integrating such projects in spatial and environmental planning (Banasiak et. Al, 2022). The report shows that Slovenia's administrative processes are significantly longer in comparison to other countries, meaning that the valid energy permits obtained for example 15 years ago are outdated due to the great progress of technology, as 1.5-megawatt wind farms are no longer either economically or environmentally acceptable, and it depends on the investors when they decide to apply for a change to the already issued permit. In addition, many permits have already expired if the investor has not completed the planned phases of work by the specified deadline (Pavlin, 2017).

1.1.5 LEGISLATION AND GOVERNMENT

Slovenian national legislation establishes, along with adopted international and EU legislation, a strong normative framework for environmental protection and posits the fight against climate change as one of the priorities of Slovenian internal as well as external action.

However, not all main Slovenian political parties reflect this reality. This was especially visible in the period between 2018 and 2022. For example, the fight against climate change was not mentioned in the 2018–2020 plan of work of the former Prime Minister’s Marjan Šarec party (List of Marjan Šarec, 2018). One of the leading parties - Slovenian Democratic Party (SDS) has also publicly denied anthropogenic climate change (Zgonik 2019). Slovenia does not have a Green party in the National Assembly, therefore a major amount of climate change and energy transition initiatives and pressure comes from NGOs and other external organisations.

1.1.6 KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Organisation	Description
The Ministry for Environment, Climate and Energy	Shapes the overall national policies and strategies in the energy sector, as well as leading all bigger energy projects
Energy Agency of Slovenia	Energy market regulator, responsible for licencing in the energy sector, responsible for granting feed-in tariff and premium
BORZEN	State-owned Power Market Operator provides and facilitate coordinated operation of the Slovenian electricity system - Via the internal centre for RES/CHP it operates the support scheme for the generation of energy from RES
ELES	State owned Transmission System Operator responsible for electricity transmission and management of the national grid
Eko sklad	The Environmental Fund of the Republic of Slovenia awards low-interest loans to renewable energy projects through a tendering process. There is a current call for applications to subsidise the reconstruction and renovation of renewable energy plants. Eligible investors

	include private and public legal entities and individuals in Slovenia. The maximum loan is for €24 million for municipalities, enterprises and other legal entities (15 years credit period) and €5 million for residents (10 years credit period).
Subsidy Scheme of the Ministry for Infrastructure	The Ministry for Infrastructure and Spatial Planning awards subsidies through a tendering process to companies that invest in energy efficiency, renewable energy and combined heating and power projects. These cover a maximum of 50 percent of an investment project's eligible costs.
SODO	SODO is a state-owned energy company in Slovenia, which performs the economic public service of the system operator of the electricity distribution network.
Local residents	
Municipalities	
NGO's	
Media	

1.2 REGIONAL CONTEXT

Introduce the case study region and reason 1) why it is interesting to look at this region specifically within the broader context that you sketched under a. Answer the question: Why is this an interesting region to look at, what is it an interesting case of? Also reason 2) which timeframe is under investigation (which period is especially interesting to focus on, i.e. the focus period?). Finally 3) introduce the 'instances of participation' that you will focus on and why.

1.2.1 REGIONAL DEMARCATION

Figure 3: Eastern Slovenia (green)

This case study will be focusing on the region of Eastern Slovenia. The cohesion region of Eastern Slovenia, which is classified as a NUTS2 region, lies at the junction of the Alps, the Pannonian Plain and the Dinaric Plain mountains. As a result, the region is geographically very diverse: the northwestern Alpine part descends towards the east and transforms into the wine-growing hills on the edge of the Pannonian plain, and to the south it rises into the karst Dinaric Mountains. It borders three countries: Austria in the north, Hungary in the east, and Croatia in east and south. The west part of the region borders the cohesion region of Western Slovenia. It has 1,089,717 inhabitants, living in 148 municipalities (RSKRVS, 2019).

1.2.1.1 Eastern Slovenia and Wind Energy

There are currently no wind energy capacities in Eastern Slovenia. Several wind energy projects are currently in development in different stages, with most being stalled due to public opposition.

List of currently active wind projects under development:

- Mislinja
- Paški kozjak
- Ojstrica
- Rogatec
- Plešivec
- Trije kralji, Rogla in Areh

There is mild wind potential in the region, as seen on the image below. The areas with wind potential are mostly hilly (Pohorje), less populated areas, mainly used for tourist activities, such as skiing resorts and recreation, including hiking, biking and skiing.

Figure 4: Areas with wind potential in Slovenia

1.2.2 LOCAL GOVERNANCE

Slovenia has no administrative regions. For the purposes of EU regional policy, it is divided into two NUTS 2 regions: Western Slovenia and Eastern Slovenia. It is also divided into 12 statistical regions at the NUTS 3 level without established ones self-government structures. Local governance is mainly limited to municipalities. Slovenia is divided into 212 municipalities, of which 11 are urban municipalities. Municipalities are bodies of local self-government and are headed by a mayor who is directly elected for a period of 4 years. The municipalities also have a municipal council, which is a municipal consultative and decision-making body consisting of members elected by general direct elections for a four-year term. It is responsible for making the main decisions, such as taking over municipal land and adopting development plans and municipal budget. The municipal council also nominates the director of the municipal administration, who is a civil servant (Kołodziejski, 2018). All other (energy-related) decision stem from the national governance bodies.

1.2.3 TEMPORAL DEMARCATION

While the first processes for building the first wind turbine in Slovenia started in 2005, DEM (Dravske elektrarne) the processes regarding the planned wind farm Ojstrica on the border between Koroška and Savinjska region began around almost 10 years later with six planned wind turbines. Currently, plans are reduced to three turbines, and formal and informal discussion on the local level is still taking place. While local community opposition to wind power plans is apparent, many other obstacles that caused such a noticeable delay exist and should be evaluated by this project.

The processes for obtaining the permits for the wind power plant are still active at the time of writing this study in 2023. The public unveiling of the draft state spatial plan and environmental report for the Ojstrica wind farm took place in 2023 between January 16 and February 17, with the local community voicing complaints and environmental concerns. Since the project is still very active at the time of research, we will follow up with the project up to and including 2023. Therefore, the time period of 2011 to 2023 is a relevant temporal demarcation for the given case study.

1.3 AIMS AND REPORT STRUCTURE

This case study focuses on exploring the development of wind energy in Eastern Slovenia, with the aim of understanding regional settings and challenges in past and current developments, as well as opportunities for future wind energy developments. Slovenia is one of the countries with least explored wind energy potential, which in itself is limited. Therefore, one of the aims of this case study is to position wind energy into a complex energy system – including technical and natural limitations, governance and policy settings, as well as social circumstances, which affect wind development (for example by exploring wind opposition). The aim is to determine which circumstances have had either positive or negative influences on wind energy deployment and through those formulate key recommendations for different stakeholders.

The report explores regional and temporal settings, including the exploration on Slovenia's energy system, subsidies, governance and bureaucratic processes, affecting wind energy deployment in chapter 1. This is followed by an overview of 3 key phases, which are divided into several critical instances of change. These explain specific events or governance changes, which affected the development of wind energy in Eastern Slovenia. The chosen period takes place from 2005 to 2023. For a better understanding of the defined phases, a pre-period is explored. This central part of the case study is followed by an analysis and synthesis. Lastly, recommendations were formulated for different stakeholders in chapter 6.

2 KEY INSIGHTS

- Strong division between supporters of wind energy projects and opposing parties, with no concrete discussion, could result in a consensus and thereafter a successful project.
- Lack of (visible) supporters for specifically wind energy – the conversation is kept around RES (as a whole, but with specific focus on solar and hydro) vs nuclear.
- No concrete strategies and plans on the national level, leading the national discourse in the direction of debating which sources to use, rather than actively building infrastructure for a successful energy transition.
- Lack of understanding and knowledge among citizens, leading to fear and opposition
- No community initiatives, which would involve citizens as an active part of the development of the projects. Citizens, especially local communities, are usually mentioned as the key stakeholder, but are still included as passive outsiders, only hearing and viewing about the project and not actively collaborating or invited to collaborate.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

This section of the case study explores the methodological tools used in this case study. A mixed method approach was used to analyse the phases and critical instances of change in the Eastern Slovenia region. The focus period of 2005 – 2023 was explored, in addition to a pre-period section for further context.

Over 50 documents have been reviewed to help understand the regional settings and contextualise the key phases. The circumstances were further explored through 5 interviews with relevant actors in wind energy development in Eastern Slovenia. Additionally, 2 events, connected to the governance changes, regarding energy system in Slovenia, were attended. The methods are described in more detail below.

3.1.1 INTERVIEWS

We conducted 5 interviews with different stakeholders, related to the development of wind energy in Slovenia. Interviews were held in person (4) or online (Microsoft Teams).

The interviewees were chosen and asked to participate, based on their role in the development of wind energy in Slovenia. Through sampling, we tried to cover a variety of relevant actors, therefore individuals working in national and local governance organisations were contacted, as well as researchers, young activists, investors and local residents of specific projects.

The interviewees were informed about the project and were given the consent form to sign. The interviews were 35 – 50 minutes long and were recorded. All interviews were done in Slovene.

After the interviews were recorded, they were transcribed, annotated and sorted into themes, to ensure best comparability. Then, interviews were compared based on the topics that were repeated in all cases.

3.1.2 DOCUMENT REVIEW

Over 50 documents have been reviewed. Due to underdevelopment of wind energy in Slovenia, a substantial part of the reviewed documents were website posts and media articles. This is due to the fact that a lot of conversations among stakeholders, particularly those opposing each other, happens through media. The analysed documents include:

- Laws and regulations
- National strategies and plans
- Research articles
- Statistical documents
- Media articles
- Local meeting reports
- Investor reports and plans

The documents were read and annotated. The opposing documents (e. g. media reports and investor plans) were compared to ensure a less biased understanding.

Additionally we've been following the civil society against the development of the Pohorje wind energy project. The society has most discussion in an open group on the social platform Facebook, where new posts are shared daily. Posts are in Slovene.

3.1.3 EVENTS

Throughout the duration of the research for this case study, we participated in events related to the development of the new energy regulation in Slovenia. We followed conversations and have seen which stakeholders have actively participated in the development of the regulations.

We observed the presentation of the National energy and climate plan to the public in April 2023, as well as subsequent discussion about the plan with different stakeholders in May 2023. This allowed us to better understand the overall energy and climate discussions in Slovenia and the role of Wind in these discussions. On both events, we participated as listeners and observers and did not actively contribute to the discussion.

3.2 EMPIRICAL REFLECTIONS

There is a lack of research done in the field of wind energy development in Slovenia, as it is still an underdeveloped energy option both nationally and regionally. The underdevelopment and the lack of research provided a challenge for this research, both for finding suitable documents and their interpretation, as well as finding suitable candidates for discussion wind energy topics in interviews. The lack of existing research meant that the majority of explored documents were media articles and governance documents (laws, acts, strategies). Additionally, available documents from investors, NGO's and other stakeholders were also explored. The lack of existing research provided an additional challenges – lack of objectivity in explored documents, especially media reports. To overcome this challenge, reports from several different media outlets were considered in specific topics.

Slovenia has no regional governance, and the small size of the country means that most issues, even local, are discussed or at least get media attention on the national level. Consequently, a focus on just Eastern Slovenia is harder to achieve. Therefore, the governance events, policies and regulations explored in the case study are mostly national, rather than regional focused. The regional focus was explored through specific wind energy projects in the region.

To ensure all stakeholder voices are heard, representatives of different groups of stakeholders were invited to participate in the case study:

- National governance representatives
- Researchers
- Local residents
- Local governance actors
- Investors
- Activists / NGOs

The final five interviews were held with a researcher, local resident, local councilor, investor and young activists.

4 WIND ENERGY GOVERNANCE IN EAST SLOVENIA

4.1 PRE-PERIOD

Slovenia's independence and first energy strategies

Slovenia started developing its own strategy for sustainable energy system development and renewable energy sources (RES) after its independence in 1991. The first regulatory basis was developed in 1996 with the adoption of the Resolution on the Strategy for the Use and Supply of Energy in Slovenia (Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia, No. 9/96). The resolution focused mainly on energy efficiency, rather than RES. Thermal and nuclear power plants, as well as hydro plants are the main energy providers for Slovenia, and these sources were planned to be further exploited by building new capacities. Renewable energy sources were considered mostly as additional options for responsible energy use, and were generally considered to be used for own production of electricity or heat in industry. They were not integrated in national energy planning capacities. When RES are mentioned, wind energy is not considered as one of the main options in this category for Slovenia. When mentioned, it's usually among the last options. Active citizen participation was not considered as such in the resolution (e. g. self-production, energy communities), however, plans to improve energy efficiency in households were set, with the main focus lying on energy education and awareness raising. Subsidies are mainly focused on improving energy efficiency (Resolution on the strategy for the use and supply of energy in Slovenia, 1996).

First energy act

In 1999, Slovenia accepted its first Energy Act. The aim of the act was to ensure the conditions for the safe and reliable supply of energy services to users according to market principles, and principles of sustainable development, taking into account its efficient use, economical use of renewable energy sources and environmental protection conditions. The law also highlighted the need to ensure competition in the energy market according to the principles of impartiality and transparency, taking into account the protection of consumers and the implementation of effective control over energy supply.

With this act, energy citizenships became regulated, with the law stating that *“the activity of electricity production in a production plant based on renewable energy sources or in cogeneration with high efficiency with a nominal power of up to 50 kW can also be performed by a natural person who submits an application for registration in the Business Register of Slovenia at the Agency for Public Legal Records and Services and who is registered in the register of declarations for production devices from renewable energy sources and cogeneration with high efficiency /.../”*. Article 65 of the Energy Act stipulated that, with the same costs for utilizing the savings potentials on the consumption side or for providing new capacities for the same amount of energy, priority is given to measures to achieve the savings potentials. The law also defines programs or instruments with which the state promotes efficient energy use and RES, namely programs of education, information, public awareness, energy consultancy, promotion of energy audits, promotion of local energy concepts, preparation of standards and technical regulations, fiscal measures, financial and other forms of incentives. Most of the prescribed incentive programs were financed from the budget of the Republic of Slovenia and financially supported mainly by the energy programs of the European Commission. (Energy Act, 1999).

Start of production from RES

While the act made energy citizenship easier, it took another 2 years for the first PV panels to be put on a roof. The first solar panels in Slovenia were put on the roof of an agency in Ljubljana and were financed by the agency. The following solar developments happened the same year as the first wind energy project started developing in Slovenia – 2005. The installation of solar panels or other RES by households took another 10 years when the costs of energy self-production became more accessible to the general public (STA, 2021).

In 2002, approximately EUR 2 million of budget funds were used to promote responsible use of energy and the use of RES within the programs prepared by the Agency for responsible use of energy. The above incentive programs were developmentally supported by the European Commission's energy programs PHARE, THERMIE, SYNERGY, SAVE and ALTENER, as well as on the basis of bilateral cooperation with individual EU member states (mainly Austria, Italy and Germany).

Qualified electricity production, i.e. the production of electricity from renewable energy sources or waste and the co-production of electricity and heat with above-average efficiency, was encouraged by favourable purchase prices for the electricity produced, which were determined by the government of the Republic of Slovenia (National Energy Programme, 2004).

National Energy Programme

The 1996 resolution was followed by the 2004 National Energy Programme. The main event that led to the development of the new plan was Slovenia becoming a member of the European Union. Slovenia ratified the Kyoto Protocol and began accession to the EU in 1999. With this Programme, Slovenia's strategies start to follow EU regulations. After a bilateral "screening" (review) for the year 2001, the Republic of Slovenia defined as its goal 33.6% of electricity produced from renewable energy sources in relation to electricity consumption by 2010. The energy law also explicitly defines promoting and prioritising RES over non-renewable sources, as well as ensuring the purchase of all produced electricity from RES at least under the same conditions as then applied on the organised market. In this programme, wind energy starts to be specifically mentioned as a possible source of electricity alongside hydro energy in plans for developing electricity generation from RES on a national level. The focus on solar remains in strategies for smaller, dispersed energy production (micro solar plants). While wind energy is highlighted, there are no specific steps on how to achieve the goals set. The programme however does conclude that the focus on wind energy should predominantly be in western parts of Slovenia, due to wind potential (National Energy Programme, 2004). Studies of wind potential were concluded after this programme was released.

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4.3 TIMELINE

Figure 5: Timeline of wind energy development within the regional Eastern Slovenia between the years of 2005 - 2023

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4.4 PHASE 1: 2005 – 2014 FIRST WIND DEVELOPMENTS AND THE START OF STRONG OPPOSITION

The entry to the EU and energy regulations EU membership brought, have turned Slovenia's energy strategy into the direction of RES. While many wind farms were already built around Europe, the first big discussion around wind energy started in Slovenia in 2005. The location in question was Volovja Reber, which to this day remains relevant for future wind projects. However in 2011, the environmental permit was taken away from the project, so its future isn't certain. Volovja reber is located in Western Slovenia.

The time frame also includes the first and second wind turbine in Slovenia, which were built in 2012 and 2014. The latter marks the end of this phase. Both turbines were also built in Western Slovenia. While this case study focuses on Eastern Slovenia, the understanding of first wind developments in Slovenia is crucial. The first wind energy projects mark the first occurrence of strong opposition against wind energy, which will follow most wind projects in Slovenia even today.

After this phase, which appeared to be the start of an active wind development, the development of wind projects stopped in Slovenia. The construction of the second wind turbine in 2014 marks the end of wind energy capacity growth in Slovenia.

4.4.1 2005 - VOLOVJA REBER WIND POWER PLANT AND FIRST OPPOSITION

The construction of the Volovja reber wind power plant was planned at the location of the same name, which has good wind potential. It's located in the municipality of Ilirska Bistrica, an area with a fairly preserved natural environment, which is the result of economic underdevelopment, although its industry used to be considered a considerable polluter of the environment.

At the beginning, the investors (Elektro Primorska, the local energy company, mostly state owned) planned 88 wind turbines. The size of the project started decreasing as the first protest from environmental activists started emerging. D. Valentinčič, the director of Elektro Primorska, described the effects of push backs to the project in an interview with a Slovenian newspaper Dnevnik. He said that the number of originally planned 88 windmills decreased first due to the demands of foresters for their corridors to 64. After carrying out environmental protection studies, the number was reduced to 47. Because of the measures to secure the area of endangered bird species, the project was further reduced to 43 windmills. The number of wind turbines was then further reduced by 10 turbines because they extended into the protected area of Natura 2000. The Agency of the Republic of Slovenia for the Environment (hereafter ARSO) issued the permit for the construction of 33 windmills. Nevertheless, after the permit was issued, further protests against the project

were started, with several different groups of stakeholders blocking the further development of the project. (Kump, 2004).

The supporters of the project, among which the biggest were the investors and the government, as well as the municipality, defended the project mainly through highlighting the economic benefits. The investor argued against comments coming from nature activists, who said the area should be protected.

The construction was opposed mainly by nature conservationists who advocated the preservation of the area and its importance for the diversity of the animal and plant world. Individuals and non-governmental organizations unanimously opposed the planned project and organized themselves into a civilian group. This is the so-called Coalition for Volovja Reber, which connected members of 28 different societies and organizations, fighting for environmental protection principles. The largest among them is the Association for the observation and study of birds in Slovenia (hereinafter DOPPS), whose members were also the most ardent opponents and gave the most arguments for why the wind farm should not be built on this site. The Institute of the Republic of Slovenia for Conservation also issued a negative nature conservation opinion on the plan and ARSO found that the proposed municipal plan was in conflict with the national plan. In 2011, the permit was revoked and the project was stopped.

4.4.2 THE CONSTRUCTION OF FIRST TWO WIND POWER PLANTS

Similar to the installation of the windmills on Volovja Rebra, the installation of the windmill at Dolenja vas was not without complications. However, in this case, it was not the nature conservationists who opposed and delayed the project, but the Ministry of the Environment. Although the investors obtained environmental approval in October 2005 and a building permit in 2009, the construction of the windmill, which had already begun, was stopped a year later, as the investors decided to change the type of the turbine. Later, they supplemented the building permits without any problems, but the first complications in the installation were caused by a report to the anti-corruption commission due to the lack of signatures of all the co-owners of the land of the Dolenja vas agrarian community. Finally, the Ministry of the Environment issued a decision on the cancellation of the amendment to the already valid construction permit, and this at the very time when the investors had already started to erect the windmill. The project, worth three million euros, stopped at that time.

While there was some opposition to the project, it mainly stemmed from local residents, who opposed the build due to visual and noise-related issues. The municipality, landowners, and environmentalists generally supported the build. The delay and issues around this project were therefore mainly connected to administrative and bureaucratic issues. They were able to continue construction only after they applied for and obtained a building permit again (Hreščak, 2009).

The second and last wind turbine was built in 2014. The investment was started by Aleš Pučnik, an independent entrepreneur from Postojna, and later it was taken over by MVE Razdrť, whose minority partners are Pučnik and the company Finbor from Vodice, while the majority partner, through a Serbian company, is the well-known Slovenian publisher Rok Kvaternik, founder of the Rokus Publishing House. The turbine is a smaller one (900 kW). The focus of this project was the support and involvement of the local community. Pučnik, in contrast with the Dolenja vas case, sought common ground with the local community, and managed to achieve it. He said in an interview: "I decided from the beginning that I would

only make the investment if a consensus was reached with the residents.” Pučnik also decided to test the effects of the turbines on the people who lived in close proximity to them, by living directly beneath them for 2 months.

The president of Razdrto Local Community, Boštjan Blažek, confirmed that even before the purchase of the land, the investor had presented his intentions to the community at a meeting of local residents, where there were no disagreements voiced towards the project. He also stated that collaboration with the local community while planning the project played a major factor in the local residents supporting the project.

4.5 2014 – 2019 STRONG OPPOSITION WITH LITTLE WIND DEVELOPMENTS

In the period between 2004, when the first National Energy Programme was developed and 2019, when the National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) was published, little was done in the area of developing comprehensive strategies or plans for a successful energy transition in Slovenia.

In this phase, Slovenia followed the regulations of the European Union. In line with the EU directive, the Slovenian government released the Action Plan for Energy Effectiveness for the Period 2014-2020, which, as the name states, focuses solely on effective use of energy and does not touch on the topic of RES deployment. Later on, in 2015, the government started developing the Energy Concept of Slovenia.

The lack of commitment to climate issues was heavily reflected in the focus and direction of the leading parties at the time. The leading parties in the phase were the Party of Miro Cerar (SMC), which ruled from 2014 to 2018, followed by the List of Marjan Šarec (LMS), who was the head of the Government from 2018 to 2020. In their term, SMC's focus in energy was on large energy facilities, such as thermal power plants, hydropower plants and nuclear power plants. Reports from that time show the dissatisfaction of several NGOs, such as Greenpeace Slovenia, with the government's ignorance towards RES (Greenpeace, 2017). The leading party, LMS, showed very little focus on energy issues, with no specific energy-related or climate-related plans in their programme.

4.5.1 2014 - 2019: DEVELOPMENTS ON MUNICIPALITY LEVELS AND OPPOSING CIVIL INITIATIVES

In the years between 2014 and 2019, a lot of smaller and bigger wind energy projects were in development by different investors in East Slovenia. By the end of 2019, five national spatial plans for wind farm fields were being prepared at the Ministry of the Environment and Spatial Planning - Mislinja, Paški Kozjak, Ojstrica, Rogatec and Plešivec. All five plans received negative reactions from the local communities. The development of all these projects was stalled if not stopped by civil initiatives, organized by local residents, usually supported by the municipalities. As of today, none of the projects have been built. In addition to these projects, additional projects are being developed in this phase, but have not yet reached the stage of applying for the building permit.

As most wind energy projects follow a similar story in Slovenia in general, we will take a look at 2 – Ojstrica and Pohorje. The development of those two projects will be discussed further in the last phase and critical instances of change.

4.5.1.1 Ojstrica

Following two successful wind energy projects, described previously, new wind energy projects started being developed across the country. Among the bigger ones in East Slovenia is the development of the wind energy plans in Koroška. In 2014, the Municipality of Dravograd adopted a municipal spatial plan with which it opened the door to builders of small and large wind power plants in the Dravograd area (Kotnik, 2017). Following this, a plan for a wind farm in the area of Ojstrica was developed by nongovernmental investors. After the plans went public in late 2014 and early 2015, the local residents seemed to support the project, as it is visible from the analysed media reports from that time. In 2015, the investor prepared an initiative for the preparation of a national spatial plan for the Ojstrica wind power plant. The Ministry of the Environment has concluded that these plans require a comprehensive environmental impact assessment.

While the investors plans envisaged eight wind turbines, according to the ornithological pre-assessment, only three wind turbines in the Ojstrica area were accepted. According to the investors' data, this meant three wind turbines of approximately 3.3 megawatts of power each in terms of the energy potential of the location, which in total amounts to approximately 10 megawatts of power and between 19 and 23 gigawatt hours of electricity produced per year. Such an investment was estimated at 11 to 13.5 million euros. All the mentioned procedures were presented at the assembly of local residents in Ojstrica by the investors, who repeatedly emphasized that they would not do anything without the consent of the residents. The residents began opposing the wind energy plans, criticizing the Municipality of Dravograd for not having enough information about what was happening and not informing them on all the possible negative impacts of the wind farm on the environment and residents. It was decided that all activities related to plans for the energy use of wind should be stopped (Kotnik, 2017).

4.5.1.2 Pohorje

A wind project, developing wind farms in three separate areas in Pohorje hills, specifically Rogla, Areh and Trije Kralji, is at the time of writing in 2023 the most talked about wind project in Slovenia. It is one of the bigger planned projects in East Slovenia, with 56 wind turbines planned, providing almost 200 MW of power.

The plans for the project started over 5 years ago but were made public in 2023. In the meantime, an environmental impact report for the mentioned area and an assessment of the cumulative impact of all wind power plant sites, access routes, the route of the cable line and distribution transformer stations, where the cable line will be connected, have already been prepared. At the time of writing, the investors are in the process of acquiring a building permit (Da., La., 2023c). While not much is known publicly about the first developments of this project in this phase, as the plans became a public interest only in 2023, according to the interviews, done for the purpose of this case study, the local residents were aware of plans for a wind farm development nearby, however the farm is said to be much smaller and farther away from local residents. The residents were said to be supportive of such developments (interviewer 4).

Figure 6: Planned Wind Turbines on Pohorje hills

4.5.2 2015 – 2018: DEVELOPMENT OF THE ENERGY CONCEPT OF SLOVENIA

In 2015, the government, then led by the Party of Miro Cerar, started developing the Energy Concept of Slovenia. The Energy Concept of Slovenia (EKS) is a strategic development document in the field of energy, which, based on the projection of the economic, environmental and social development of the country and on the basis of accepted international obligations, sets the goals for a reliable, sustainable and competitive energy supply for the next 20 or 40 years. The concept is described on the government's website to provide, in accordance with the Energy Act, the directions and vision of Slovenia's energy policy. The strategic document is a document of a guiding nature and therefore does not define individual concrete projects. It establishes a political framework within which business initiatives by companies and individuals can work on developing energy projects. The document sets three main pillars for Slovenian future in energy: environmental acceptability, reliability of energy supply and competitiveness in the energy market (Energy Concept of Slovenia, n. d.)

4.6 2019 - ... CLIMATE AND ENERGY POLICY PUSH

From 2019, when the first NECP draft was made public, and now, energy related topics have gained momentum in all areas of the society. Energy, which was before something citizens did not pay much attention to, became the centre of policy, media and societal conversations in general. This can be due to several circumstances, which have drastically changed the energy sector in the EU. The energy crisis, which was highlighted even more by the Russian-Ukraine war, the growing costs of energy, as well as ever more visible consequences of

climate change, have meant that citizens, who might not have thought about energy and energy-related topics before, have now joined the conversations. Situations like this offer both challenges and opportunities. With more people interested in the topic, there are opportunities for developing community energy projects and making the energy sector less centralised, however the downfall, visible also in Slovenia, might be the lack of knowledge about energy-related topics among citizens, which results in media conversations, saturated with fear-mongering and false information.

The focus on energy has also meant that the new policies, developed by the government, mostly due to requirements from the EU, were under the watchful eye of the entire country. With the whole country watching, the government does not want to make a wrong decision and has therefore resorted to passing this responsibility to citizens, aiming to make a decision based on a referendum, which will focus on the two scenarios offered. The lack of knowledge and understanding among citizens can lead to uninformed decisions in the referendum and makes this decision a political question, rather than a scientific one.

While this phase is looking brighter for wind energy in Slovenia, than the previous one, it is still surrounded by a feeling of indecision and doubt due to lack of concrete decisions and still visible opposition. The discussion on energy sources in Slovenia is heavily focused on nuclear vs RES, which often results in strong opposition from both sides and no definitive answers as to how to proceed with the energy transition.

4.6.1 NECP 2019

During 2019, Slovenia has been engaged in a complex process of preparing the NECP, which also encompassed its Strategic Environmental Assessment and initiated a wide climate and energy discourse in the country. Improving energy and resource efficiency in all sectors and therefore reducing consumption of energy and other natural resources has been set as the first and key measure on a path towards a climate-neutral society. As the first national energy plan adopted after 2004, the NECP set ambitious energy and climate objectives for Slovenia until 2030: reduction of total GHG emissions by 36%, reduction of GHG emissions in the non-ETS sector by 20% (according to the EU Effort Sharing Regulation the Slovenian target is -15%), an increase of energy efficiency for at least by 35% (EU target is 32.5%), and investment in research and development in the amount of at least 3% of GDP (of which public funding amounts to 1%; Government of the Republic of Slovenia 2020). In parallel, Slovenia did not set any target regarding energy connectivity since it already significantly exceeded the EU target for 2030, whereas the objective for RES remained cautiously unambitious on account of above mentioned relevant national circumstances, i.e. at least 27% of renewable sources (while the EU target is 32%).

The reduction of energy consumption and GHG emissions is widely supported by the public and non-governmental sector, whereas there is a major divide regarding the national target on the use of renewable energy until 2030. On the one hand, a part of the non-governmental sector and public argue that the country should adopt a much higher target (e.g. up to 45%), on the other hand, a part of the non-governmental sector and public strongly opposes any further construction of HPPs and WPPs (Ministry of Infrastructure, 2019). Moreover, the Strategic Environmental Assessment of the NECP resulted in the exclusion of the proposed construction of large HPPs on the River Sava until 2030, consequently contributing to a less ambitious renewable energy target for 2030 and the outlook for a long-term energy transition towards a climate-neutral society without significant increase of the electricity import dependency, unless a new nuclear unit is built.

There was a general dissatisfaction with the NECP from all sides, particularly the industry, and NGOs. Among those is a movement called Youth for Climate Justice, which developed as part of the Fridays for Future movement. Their protest and vocal dissatisfaction with the plan as well as their willingness to be involved has resulted in an invitation from the Ministry of Infrastructure to participate in debates around the development of NECP. However, this call was made very late, when most of the plan was already drafted and the deadlines were near.

The low quality of the NECP was also proven in the European Climate Foundation's report assessing all the Member States' integrated National Climate and Energy Plan drafts, which were submitted to the European Commission. Among all 28 countries that were analysed, Slovenia received the lowest score of only 3.2%. As described by the European Climate Foundation, this report assesses all the Member States' draft integrated National Climate and Energy Plans submitted to the European Commission and scores them according to the level of ambition, the level of detail of the policies and measures described, and the quality and inclusiveness of the drafting process.

4.6.2 NECP 2023 AND TWO SCENARIOS: NUCLEAR VS RES

In 2022, Slovenia started drafting a new NECP, after dissatisfaction with the one accepted in 2019. The draft was presented to the public in March of 2023.

The updating of the NECP is taking place intertwined with the previously presented activities and will be based on the parallel creation of updated goals until 2030 and 2040 and the necessary measures to achieve these goals.

The Ministry for Environment, Climate and Energy has stated that based on previous experience, they will actively strive for good cooperation with the drafters of the environmental report. For this NECP, different scenarios were developed, with the aim of a joint search for environmentally acceptable solutions and the creation of scenarios in accordance with the requirements of the comprehensive environmental impact assessment. Two scenarios were developed – the first focuses solely on renewables, while the second combines renewables with nuclear, including a new nuclear reactor. The second nuclear reactor has been in the planning phase for several years in Slovenia and it is currently still one of the key topics in discussion related to Slovenia's energy transition.

Both scenarios were presented in the unveiling of NECP in March 2023, which we participated in as part of this research. Due to the controversy around the development of nuclear power plants, the discussion about nuclear energy vs. RES was the focus of the event. The representatives of the Government, present at the event, remained neutral towards the scenarios, a position the Government kept throughout all discussions about NECP. When asked about making the decision about a preferred scenario, a decision they have been criticised for not having accepted yet, the government removed itself from the discussion, while presenting both scenarios as equally as possible. They have determined that the final decision should be made by the public in a referendum. The decision, according to the document, should be made by 2027. The lateness of the decision year and the shifting of responsibility was met with a lot of criticism, especially from the industry, stakeholders from the energy sector and some NGOs. The government justified their decision by stating that there is simply not sufficient information and research done at the moment to determine which scenario is more suitable.

The debate around nuclear power was the main topic of conversation at the event, preventing most other topics from being discussed. The focus on nuclear also meant that renewables were packed and presented as a single entity, without specifying specific goals for individual sources. Therefore, wind energy was not individually discussed at the event or discussions in media and further events, following the release of the draft.

The new NECP, like the previous one, raised a lot of dissatisfaction in the public. The industry particularly has voiced a lot of dissatisfaction, as well as NGOs and organisations such as Youth for Climate Justice.

The development of two scenarios is of crucial importance for the development of wind energy in Slovenia. Choosing the RES scenario would mean that all possible renewable energy sources should be used, including wind energy, which as of now, doesn't provide much energy in Slovenia. If the nuclear scenario is chosen, it might stall the development of wind energy, as there'll be less need for RES production. The percentages of energy production that have to come from RES might stem more from solar power plants, which are rapidly growing in Slovenia and are generally better accepted.

Participation practice 2: Youth for Climate Justice

This participation practice focuses on a national level participation in decision-making processes. Youth for Climate Justice is a movement that developed as part of the Friday's for future international movement.

They are a self-organized, democratic and diverse movement of more than a hundred individuals from all over Slovenia. They state their aim as a decent life for everyone on a preserved planet. Their main members are young activists from across Slovenia, from different fields and with different levels of education.

While not said directly, a lot of their work is dedicated to ensuring justice in all climate topics, including energy. According to their website, they fight for concrete measures that are friendly to people and the environment, and in the long term build an alternative to the system of exploitation of people and nature. They organize everything from reading groups, lectures and workshops to actions in public spaces, cultural interventions and protests. Through this, they demand measures and propose concrete solutions for specific issues raised. In their demand, regarding the energy policy, they state that the design of all green transition measures should be made in such a way as to preserve and improve the standard of living of less wealthy, particularly marginalized social groups. They add that vulnerable individuals and households should be provided with sufficient assistance to implement green transition measures.

Because of their visibility, they have been invited by the Ministry for Environment, Climate and Energy to participate in several discussions in the formation of the NECP. They have also actively participated in other climate-related events. During the unveiling of the last NECP, they voiced their dissatisfaction with the plan, which they also shared in an open letter to the Ministry for Environment, Climate and Energy. They have accused the plan of being the 'Plan for the Climate Breakdown', stating that the plan is not ambitious, not sufficient and not appropriate. The open letter, which they have shared with the Ministry in the public unveiling phase of the NECP, states that Slovenia sets minimal goals and is led by corrupt ideas.

They stated 4 main demands for the ministry:

1. Raising climate goals and preventing climate collapse: the document should be in line with scientific findings and the Paris Agreement, which foresees a reduction of emissions by at least 65% by 2030 compared to 2020.
2. Ending the myth of green capitalism: the document should stop tracking the endless growth of consumption and production, leaving the green transition in the hands of capital, strengthens the power of public, community and state actors and focuses on the true well-being of people and nature.
3. Enabling a free path for the full flowering of nature: the document should omit all references to the need to destroy nature to achieve decarbonisation, should limit using biomass only on wood scraps and delete references to the construction of hydroelectric power plants.
4. The main culprits of the climate crisis should pay for the transition: the funds for the transition to a low-carbon society should primarily be contributed by those who are most responsible for the collapse - owners of capital and the rich. These funds should be used to prevent the worsening of the situation for working people, and finance measures that are friendly to workers and the climate

Their open letter was supported and signed by 48 organizations, including big NGO's, such as Greenpeace Slovenia and Umanotera.

4.6.3 NEW LAW ON THE INTRODUCTION OF DEVICES FOR THE PRODUCTION OF ELECTRICITY FROM RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES

The new legislation, which was passed in July 2023, oversees the organization of space and permits, primarily focusing on wind parks and solar power plants. It outlines the process for designating priority areas for photovoltaic facilities, including larger roofs, closed landfills, and energy and transportation infrastructure. Additionally, it serves as a foundation for identifying favorable locations. The new law also addresses the approval process for network connections and equipment, including energy storage systems.

Photovoltaic installations are now mandatory for larger buildings, such as those with roofs, car parks, energy infrastructure surroundings, roads, railways, closed landfills, and quarries. Restrictions on renewables were lifted for degraded agricultural land, with provisions for agrivoltaics, and exemptions for open-cast mining pits, artificial lakes on former surface mines, and unprotected forests.

The legislation was deemed necessary to access European resilience funds. It establishes test centers for new technologies, outlines conditions for research concessions for geothermal power systems, and grants municipalities one-time compensation for facilitating wind park installations. Permitting procedures were streamlined, allowing photovoltaic facilities on joint property with a reduced share of co-owners accepting the project.

4.6.4 POHORJE AND OJSTRICA – THE DEVELOPMENTS

The two projects we explored in the previous phase have gone through a lot of change during this time frame. Both are still actively talked about, with changes happening everyday.

4.6.4.1 Ojstrica

The public unveiling of the draft state spatial plan and environmental report for the Ojstrica wind power plant took place between January 16 and February 17 this year. The opposition to the project locally remained active. Dravograd Municipality Mayor Anton Preksavec said that the municipality will insist on protecting water resources, while the local residents were mainly voicing concerns about the noise and the impact on their health and the protection of water sources (it was perceived that the wind farm could impact the quality of their water resources). The visibility of the wind farms from nearby farms was also one of the main complaints, voiced not only by residents but also by some nationwide NGOs.

The Ministry organised several meetings with the local community and addressed their concerns with several environmental and other impact studies of the wind turbines. However, the opposition remains strong to this day. Despite this, the government and investors keep working on developing the projects further, which have been in the works for over 8 years now.

4.6.4.2 Pohorje

The plans to build the wind farms on Pohorje were revealed to the public in early 2023. The project was met with instant disapproval of municipalities and local communities in the vicinity. A civil initiative was developed in May 2023, which strongly opposed all plans and accused the investors and the government of corruption and deception. This is due to the fact that the project was split into 3 separate building permit applications. This proves, in the opinion of the municipalities, that the investors are trying to bypass the approval procedure of the national spatial plan, which would take longer. Smaller projects, however, can be approved without being part of the national spatial plan.

The most vociferous opposition to the project is in Slovenska Bistrica, where a civil initiative was established for this purpose. The municipal council unanimously approved the mandatory interpretation of spatial planning conditions in the municipality's area, with which investors in wind farms were additionally warned that they could build only small wind farms up to a nominal power of one megawatt in areas of agricultural land.

At the same time, the municipality is convinced that the state should take the leading role in such projects and that the investor in such a large project should apply for a change in the state spatial plan, but not avoid this by breaking the project into several smaller ones. The latter is permitted by the legislation if it concerns wind farms with a power of less than ten megawatts (interviewee 4).

In September, the councillors of the municipality of Slovenska Bistrica officially expressed their opposition to the construction of wind farms in Pohorje.

Other municipalities in the vicinity also are not satisfied with the project, stating similar reasons for their dissatisfaction. The municipal councillors of Ruše also unanimously rejected the already confirmed signing of the agreement on easement rights for the construction of the cable line in 2021, and at the same time called on the government to stop the process of placing wind farms in Pohorje.

The investors are fighting negative perceptions by promising benefits for the municipal treasury, the replacement of felled trees, the construction of additional roads that would also benefit tourism and the restoration of those that would be damaged during construction. The residents living closest to the project would be provided with free or cheaper electricity according to the energy community model.

Participation practice 2: Civil initiatives against Wind Farms at Pohorje

As mentioned before, after the unveiling of the plans for the wind farm in Pohorje, which is currently the biggest wind project in East Slovenia, local residents of the Municipality of Slovenska Bistrica formed a civil initiative. The initiative is called ZA Pohorje brez vetrnic (FOR Pohorje without wind turbines) and has been active in the opposition since May 2023. One of their first visible activities was a protest in May, where over 50 people joined in to protest the plans. They have continued their activities with several petitions and open letters to the investors, the municipality and the Ministry for the Environment, Climate and Energy (intervieww 4).

The initiative is strongly against any kind of wind projects in Pohorje. After the first initiative was developed in Slovenska Bistrica, additional civil initiatives were organised in 4 neighbouring municipalities, all with the same aim. The initiatives work together to prevent further developments of the project and to assure the involvement of local residents in the decision making process, regarding the spatial planning of the project. The spatial planning on national level includes a public discussion phase, while the local processes are much less inclusive. There is, however, at least a 30 day timeframe for complaints against municipalities decisions.

The members of the initiative organise protests, open letters and petitions. They are actively involved in discussions on the municipal level. They are strongly against any kind of wind farm developments in the area and are therefore not welcoming any kind of discourse (interviewee 1). As is evident from the comments in the Facebook group, they perceive any communication with the investors as an opportunity for the investors to deceive or even bribe others into supporting the project. Several members are more prominent, while others remain in the background, joining only bigger events (protests). The visible members also participate in the discussion in the media, giving interviews and sharing their opinion. Together, they have informed the Prime Minister Robert Golob, Ministers Bojan Kumer and Alenka Bratušek, the investors, as well as the President of the country Nataša Pirc Musar, who allegedly failed to respond to their request for half a year, that they would resolutely rise to the goal of preventing Pohorje becoming a technologically polluted and due to wind farms also at risk of fire.

The major complaints of the initiative revolve around:

- The number of wind turbines planned. The initiatives believe that for a residential area, with active tourism and protected environmental areas, the planned project is too big. They have often stated that had the project been smaller, the opposition might not be as strong.
- Lack of communication from investors. The initiatives are of the opinion that the investors failed to include them in the planning process, and informed them about the plans too late. While some residents knew of the fact that there was a plan for a wind farm in the area, they have noted (as per media reports), that did not know the details of the plans (interviewee 5).
- Safety concerns. The local residents are concerned about several safety issues, including the safety of water resources, which are all in the area where the turbines are planned to be built, and fire safety.
- Noise and visual pollution. Residents have voiced several concerns about the impact of the noise on their quality of life. The planned wind turbines are supposedly positioned as close as 350 m from the closest residential building. Due to well developed tourism in the area, the residents are also concerned about the visual pollution of the turbines in the otherwise natural environment.

The initiatives have strong support from the municipalities. The support stems both from the issues with the project, described above (fragmentation of permitting applications), as well as strong consensus against the wind farm among all local communities (if the municipality would go against local residents, they would lose supporters).

Since the civil initiative was organised, the investors have tried to meet with local residents, but they have reportedly been met with declines (interviewee 1).

Figure 7: Local protest

5 ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

As it has been shown, Slovenia is, compared to its neighbouring and other similar countries, a complicated case study of wind energy development. As we have shown through the research, there are several reasons for this.

Natural limitations

The first reason could be defined as natural limitations. Slovenia does not have as much wind potential as other neighbouring countries. Additionally, a lot of the areas with winds strong and consistent enough for wind energy farms are part of Natura 2000 or are otherwise protected for environmental reasons. Additionally, as it was also discussed with interviews, Slovenia also lacks degraded areas, as its population is quite scattered throughout the country. This means that there are rarely places which are not environmentally protected and at the same time not populated, limiting potential areas for the development of bigger wind farms. Nevertheless, smaller farms could be built in several areas. For this reason, a comprehensive overview of potentially suitable areas for the exploitation of wind energy was ordered to be done in 2015 by the Ministry of Infrastructure. Eastern Slovenia particularly lacks areas where wind farms could be built without being close to settlements.

Lack of concrete and comprehensive national climate and energy strategy

The second reason for the underdeveloped exploitation of wind energy, as was also noted in all interviews, lies with poorly defined national plans. Slovenia, to this day, lacks a comprehensive plan for its energy transition. While existing plans do state some goals and strategies on how to achieve them, there are no concrete or definite plans, which would act as a guideline for investors, local and national governance and all other stakeholders. In 2023, Slovenia is still debating two possible scenarios for energy transition, one including nuclear and renewable sources and the other focusing solely on renewables. If the latter is chosen, both solar and wind energy capacities would have to grow immensely to satisfy the electricity demand in Slovenia, which will likely, due to electrification of transport, heating and cooling, as well as general digitalisation, grow in the upcoming decades. This decision would provide a justification that could be used by investors, as well as decision and policy makers in their discussion with opposition. As this decision has not been made yet, the conversation about the future of electricity production in Slovenia still often heavily revolves around the nuclear option, with either side not having a strong strategic foundation to rely on. To summarize, there is a lot of talk and strategizing in Slovenia's energy policy, but no concrete plans are finalized.

Lengthy bureaucratic processes

Next, the issue that kept appearing in both the interview with the investors, and media content, are the long bureaucratic processes. Due to this, the length of the projects is often longer than 3 years, which is additionally prolonged by the strong opposition which follows most wind projects. This issue was addressed in the Law on the introduction of devices for the production of electricity from renewable energy sources, which was put in motion in July 2023, however the investors have raised concerns that the act does not improve the processes as much as it was meant to. As the act is new, the final verdict on this has not been reached yet.

Strong and loud opposition

The fourth reason for complications is the strong local opposition that follows all energy projects in Slovenia. This is a complex issue in Slovenia. As discussed in the interview with the energy researcher, this might stem from bad experiences from the first wind energy project in Slovenia. Due to its positioning in a conflicting area (the area has strong wind potential, but concerns were raised by nature conservationists, due to the area being part of the bird migration route), the projects, which could be an example of a successful wind energy installation, became a controversial topic, which as a result cast a bad light on wind energy in general. Due to Slovenia being a small country, issues like this are discussed on a national level, meaning most citizens were informed and aware of this project and its challenges. Consequently, every wind project after to this day still brings up the negative connotations of Volovja Reber and all other unsuccessful wind projects. Due to the lack of successful wind installations, it is more difficult to fight the negative perception of wind energy. The local opposition has been noted in all past and current wind energy projects. Due to scattered settlements, opposition and concerns also often stem from the placement of the planned wind farms, as they are almost never positioned completely away from residential areas.

As we can see in this brief overview, we can identify two groups of stakeholders in Slovenia, mostly standing on opposing poles. On the opposition side we can usually find local governance organisations (municipalities in the case of Slovenia), local residents, and most nature conservation NGOs. The supporters of the projects are usually national governance bodies, investors, and some NGOs. Their roles in the deployment (or lack thereof) differ. Having no regional governance which could provide regional plans and strategies in Eastern Slovenia, and the lack of clear, comprehensive and realistic plans for wind energy development in Slovenia, which should be defined by the government and the Ministry of Environment, Climate and Energy, means laws, processes and most of all paths to decarbonisation of the energy sector in Slovenia are open to interpretation and manipulation. This includes potential areas for wind energy farms, clear rules and limitation on the placement of the turbines, and other limitations, as well as clear and definite goals. Although the national government supports the deployment of wind energy as seen in the plans and strategies they develop, they avoid showing public support to specific wind projects in development.

As a result, since wind projects in Slovenia are led by private investors, we can see examples of those investors omitting the active integration of all relevant stakeholders in the processes of developing projects and even looking for loopholes in the regulations. Additionally, investors also stand alone in their promotion of the project, and subsequent discussions with local authorities, citizens and communities, without vocal public support from national or local governance. The investors are often painted by the media and local communities as the bad guys in the story of wind energy deployment (whether that is true or not), led by capital and ready to manipulate the local environment for monetary gains. National governing bodies however, despite setting wind energy goals, for which many wind capacities should be built, mostly remain silent in the situation and act solely as the permitting intermediaries. The responsibility for the success of the project therefore remains solely with the investors.

The local governments' responsibilities are permitting processes for smaller energy projects (below 10 MW). In wind projects however, noticeably, they often take the side of the local communities in their opposition to the projects. The reason behind this might be political, as the municipal governance actors need their citizens' approval and support for their reelection. With the lack of citizen support in local municipalities, local governance takes the opinion of the majority, which is usually against the project.

Local citizens are considered by most other actors (investors, government) to have a passive role in the development of the wind projects, meaning stakeholders mostly strive for their acceptance, rather than active collaboration (interviewees 1 and 4). While special attention is paid to local citizens by the investors, including organising meetings, preparing informing leaflets and using other communication tactics, they are usually not part of the conceptualisation phase of the project. In fact, local citizens are usually informed about the project, once the permitting process has already started. According to media reports, citizens of Pohorje have not been informed about the development of the project or involved into discussion about the project until early 2023, when the investors started the process of applying for building permits. As mentioned before, the applications for building permits were fragmented, in opinion of the citizens and local governance to avoid longer permitting processes of the national spatial planning.

The manipulation of the permitting process and lack of communication from the investors side has resulted in a strongly negative perception of the project among local stakeholders. The lack of communication and involvement of citizens is strongly visible in other projects as well.

On the other hand, in one of the two successful wind energy projects, citizens were involved in the process from the planning phase of the project, and were invited to share opinions, ideas and concerns. Their opinions were considered, which led to a successful project. However, it must be noted that in this case, we are talking about one wind turbine, while other projects involve a larger number of bigger wind turbines. As per information shared with us (interview 4), residents of Pohorje were also informed about a smaller wind energy project, involving a few smaller wind turbines, which they were in favour of, since they were consulted before the project was fully developed. While we do not know what would happen once such a project would go public, we can deduce from available information that projects of a smaller scale, where citizens could get more actively involved in the planning, are more likely to be well accepted and supported in the local environment. Due to the geographical and features (wind potential, settlements) of Slovenia, such a project might also be more suitable.

One of the biggest concerns local residents raise is the noise element, since often, the turbines are positioned close to residential areas. Additionally, residents are concerned about nature preservation, particularly water safety, forest preservation and the impact on animals. The last point raised oftenly is the visual element, particularly in the areas where tourism is active, and the impact wind farms might have on it.

While the notion of energy justice is almost never mentioned directly, its elements are embedded in discussions around wind energy projects, particularly about the environmental aspects of justice, as well as energy sovereignty of the local residents. When asked about energy justice, it is clear that every interviewees understands the concepts differently. Most have focused on aspects or recognition and procedural justice (interviewees 2, 4, 5), naming the lack of citizen involvement in procedures as one of the key issues. They consider aspects such as the quality of life and the wind turbines effect on it (whether that is noise, visual pollution or other issues), electricity price etc. Similar understanding can be noticed in the media. While financial incentives (e. g. cheaper energy) are mentioned, they are rarely

perceived as positive. Often, they are viewed as 'buying out supporters' or as 'bribes'. Justice was often when discussed with the interviewees, interpreted very narrowly – mostly as the wind projects doing no harm to local residents or to some extent the benefits outweighing the disadvantages. Distributive justice was never mentioned.

To summarize, Eastern Slovenia's wind energy development is heavily impacted by a polar division between the wind energy project's supporters and their opposition, with no visible or willing intermediaries that could mediate this process. While new laws have been developed in order to support the deployment of renewable sources, they are expected to have a much more positive effect on solar development than wind. The laws do not address the issues of citizen involvement, but are rather focused on improving permitting processes, as well as dedicating part of the profits of the renewable sources infrastructure to local municipalities. Due to the size of wind energy projects, they are often considered as larger infrastructural impositions in contrast to solar PV, making the process of deployment much more complicated.

6 SYNTHESIS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

As described in the analysis, there are several issues and challenges which limit the deployment of wind energy in Eastern Slovenia. When discussing the issues with interviewees, one issue stood out from the rest – the lack of a concise and specific energy policy, strategy and plans on a national level. However, other issues were raised and also deducted from the overview of the documents. We have divided the recommendations based on the stakeholders they apply to.

National governance bodies:

- Define a clear energy transition strategy, which would serve as the foundation for all energy-related decisions in investments and prevent neverending discussions about the suitability of different energy sources.
- Define clear requirements for wind energy turbines (e. g. distance from residential areas), which would prevent open discussion on the suitability of planned locations.
- Predict planned areas for wind energy development and include them in national energy strategies.
- Simplify legislation to reduce barriers for new and existing wind energy projects. Bureaucracy, legislative and administrative burdens are an issue most investors face when planning wind energy projects in Slovenia. Particularly the length of the project planning phase is too long, adding additional costs to the projects.
- Inform and raise awareness about wind energy, the effect of the turbines on health, quality of life and natural environment, as well as widen the discussion, acknowledging both the pros and the cons of wind energy and how it can help realise the countries climate and energy goals

Local authorities:

- Develop local climate/energy strategies, which define how a specific municipality can contribute to the energy transition. Include all relevant local stakeholders, including citizens, industry and tourism organisations. Such strategies and local considerations might provide opportunities and support bottom-up energy project development.
- Develop mediation agencies for the facilitation of the discussions on energy projects in development in a specific municipality.

Investors:

- Include all relevant local stakeholders in the planning phase of the projects. Consider stakeholder's questions and concerns.
- Do not focus solely on financial compensation for local residents. Allow them to actively join local projects.

- Consider smaller wind energy projects. Due to Slovenia's geographical features and the fragmentation of settlements, such projects might be more successful, as they also represent a less intense environmental encroachment.

7 ANNEX 1: BIBLIOGRAPHY

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8 ANNEX 2: INTERVIEWEES

	Role	Date	Duration
Interviewee 1	Representative of a Wind Energy Farm Investor company in Slovenia	September 20 th 2023	45 min
Interviewee 2	Young energy activist, working in the energy business	October 17 th 2023	55 min
Interviewee 3	Researcher at University of Ljubljana, focusing on climate and energy policy and governance	October 3 rd 2023	35 min
Interviewee 4	Slovenska Bistrica local governance councilor	October 10 th 2023	45 min
Interviewee 5	Local resident of Pohorje region	August 20 th 2023	35 in

9 ANNEX 3: MEETINGS AND EVENTS ATTENDED

- The public unveiling of the first draft of the updated National energy and climate plan in Ljubljana, April 4th 2023. The event marked the opening of a month-long public debate on the NECP. Representative of the government and the leaders of the NECP process attended and presented the draft. The presentation was followed by a discussion.
- Meeting of the Strategic Council for the Energy Transition at the Chamber of Commerce and Industry, May 8th 2023. The meeting was dedicated to a discussion on the draft of the new NECP. It was attended by representatives from the energy sector, industry, young activity initiatives and government representatives.